

RHYTHMIC SKILLS OF BLIND AND PARTIALLY SIGHTED CHILDREN FORMATION METHODS

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Abstract. This article talks about methods of formation of rhythmic skills of blind and partially sighted children through musical rhythmic activities, teacher's pedagogical skills and activities.

According to the Orastu mayor's book "Rhetorika," physically healthy and beautiful young people are the wealth of any country. How to achieve such features? Those who engage in physical education in family and school conditions are brought up as well-rounded people through timely self-education, intellectual education, and adaptation to manners education.

It is useful for performing choreographic exercises and human movements at one tempo in a beautiful and meaningful way. Music is seen as a miraculous force influencing living beings, gods, nature and the universe with divine and magical powers.

In the formation of rhythmic skills of blind and partially sighted children, special attention was paid to the mastery and development of musical-rhythmic movements in preschool education institutions and primary school students.

Also, through rhythmic movements, along with the musical and rhythmic abilities of students, their moral and spiritual condition is formed. They quickly develop the ability to perceive rhythm. Some of them have very low reception characteristics.

According to the requirements of DTS, students should: improve metro rhythm, basic hand positions, basic foot positions, and main elements of foot-dance, increase the artistic activity of foot-dance skills, increase multifaceted aspects of musical composition, and know the structure of a musical work.

It is planned to teach musical and rhythmic movements in preschool educational institutions. To music leaders and music teachers:

1. Teaching to perform actions in the character of music;
2. Musical development tools: performing movements by sensing the rhythm, playing musical dances, using choirs, regularly using dance movements during other artistic amateur activities;
3. Systematization of work with children, use of a diversity of organization;
4. He emphasizes that he should carry out rhythmic exercises together with his teachers and give advice on improving their musical level [2].

In the boarding school textbooks, there is some information about dance movements from the science of music. For example: in the textbook of the 3rd grade, special attention was paid to folk music and dances. The 4th-grade music textbook also provides some information about

individual dances. But this is not enough for these children, they cannot have enough understanding of dance, therefore, the music teacher's follow-up, continuous work on himself, and pedagogic skills provide students with rhythmic movements and sufficient information about dance. It is appropriate for them to try to give.

The use of advanced methods and the effective use of modern technical means in providing information about dance movements of national, ancient, and peoples of the world will give effective results.

Such methods are very useful in forming their rhythm characteristics. Skillful use of the clapping method, rhythmic movements, and elements of dance in the process of training or extracurricular activities will have a particularly good effect on their sense of rhythm.

The art of dance has been widely developed in Central Asia and other nations since ancient times. They expressed their holidays, feelings of joy, and their feelings through musical rhythmic movements and their dances.

Since the 19th century, the art of dance has been called "Choreography". The dance moves are also given through written content using well-known characters. The term choreography was introduced by the French dance teacher R. Foye (1700) [1].

Archaeological excavations conducted in some regions of Uzbekistan show that spirituality and culture have deep roots in these lands.

Rhythm is derived from the Greek word rhythms, which means one smooth flow. Rhythm is the relationship between long and short dimensions of sounds in musical works of art. Each piece of music has its rhythm method. The sound of the music is related to the rhythm. There is no trauma without rhythm, the types of rhythm include meter and measures.

Rhythmic movements play an important role in the education of blind and partially sighted children.

Folk dances with rhythmic movements, especially circle dances, have rich and complex aspects of rhythm. Circle methods-performer, musicians, and residents are accompanied by musical instruments or dance, and through dance, they learn rhythmic features.

In the 4-5th grade music textbook, there are notes about $4/4$ and $6/8$. In the course of the lesson, he can make movements with his hands to measure these dimensions. It depends on the physical and mental characteristics of children. We teach children in groups according to their interests. In this case, we divide each row into an array of one size:

Group 1 - $2/4$ size;

2nd group - $3/4$ size;

3rd group - $4/4$ size;

Group 4 - size $6/8$.

To the accompaniment of a musical instrument, arenas of various sizes are performed, and the groups must quickly determine the size that belongs to them, which corresponds to the geometrical angles (four corners, four corners, three corners, hexagon, two corners, oval) can be geometric solid paper materials. Having determined the content of the song, the children show the geometric angles in their hands, and it is necessary to perform activities with rhythmic movements added to them. The dance moves continue like this. Points are deducted from groups that do not know their size. They work hard to score goals, and they are motivated. At the end of the lesson, points are calculated and winners are determined. Rated by active participants or groups. This lesson process is monitored by the music leader of the boarding school, and the educator reminds the student to repeat these tasks at other times as

a reflection. To use this didactic practice in the course of the lesson, the pedagogue must be skilled to understand their physiology, psychology, and their soul, because their hearts are delicate.

Such rhythmic dance movements encourage children to reduce their defects, develop their senses, and create feelings of joy.

For blind and partially sighted children, tapping their feet to marching songs, using marching movements, marching in place, and entering images will help them perceive music, and these actions will help them feel the music and get an education.

Each piece is changed according to the wishes of the children. After hearing each line they sing, they start singing along. When the song changes, the marching group stops, and another group starts marching. Each group walks in the direction it wants, so the groups join together and take a step together. These actions depend on the skill of the music educator or leader.

If dances and rhythmic movements educate physically if they are didactic dances, they will help them to think, calculate, correct, and strengthen their knowledge, and these movements will serve the child's education in a comprehensive manner [3].

Each didactic action has a certain purpose, and task, and adds joy to the students. However, the teachers must prevent the safety of blind children before they play each dance, and their actions must be under control.

Musical and rhythmic educational tools include the following tasks:

1. Aimed at strengthening the child's physical activity and health. Comprehensive education of body structure;
2. Formation of musical movement and skills;
3. Educating from a spiritual and aesthetic point of view;
4. Strengthen memory and attention;
5. To expand the worldly scientific point of view and educate politeness.

The means of musical-rhythmic education are music and movement. There are the following means of musical and rhythmic education:

1. Music literacy;
2. Ensuring harmony of movement with music;
3. Musical dances;
4. Actions specific to dance;
5. step and run;
6. Activities performed without music;
7. National and modern dance movements;
8. It consists of rhythmic physical training.

Rhythmic movements and dances of blind and partially sighted children are appropriate if they are conducted as rhythmic gymnastics to music, morning physical education sessions, and classes. Such activities increase the spiritual level of a person and help him feel refreshed and healthy throughout the day. Their health and appearance improve, they look forward to marriage, their physical activity increases, and it is of great importance for the proper development of children.

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